

Safarov E. Y.

Doctor of Technical Sciences, Professor
Bakhtiyorova (Nazirova) D.Sh

National University of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5982202>

POSSIBILITIES OF USING THE GIS PROGRAMS – "ARCGIS", "FREEHAND" AND "MAPINFO" IN DEMOGRAPHY MAPPING

Abstract. *Interaction of GIS technologies and cartography in the form of geo-mapping opens up new possibilities for cartography and changes its perspectives. The development of operative map making, animations in cartography are the results of interaction mentioned above. This article touches the changes in such areas map creation and map editing. How all the stages of map creation and editing are transformed with GIS and how they become more accessible for common users.*

Introduction. One of the most important problems of the current stage of informatization of society and the economy is a significant increase in the level and volume of the use of information technologies. In particular, there is an acute problem of expanding the scope of GIS and GIS technologies in industries operating in the surrounding space. The interaction of geoinformatics and cartography has become the basis for the formation of a new direction - geoinformation mapping, the essence of which is automated information and cartographic modeling of natural and socio-economic geosystems based on GIS and knowledge bases. In the foreseeable future, the prospects for the development of cartography in the geosciences are associated primarily and almost entirely with geoinformation mapping. This is due to the increasing requirements for the efficiency of managing the infrastructure of territories, the financial and economic activities of enterprises, engineering networks and communications, which require continuous improvement of information support systems. Therefore, only information systems that use a well-built geographic information system (GIS), designed to provide reliable information about the spatial position of objects and their state, are able to effectively cope with the task. For a long time, cartographic data served as the main source of data for spatial databases, including geographic information systems. The card as an information carrier performs two functions:

- positional (gives information about the exact location of the object, about its size);
- attributive (informs about the type, kind, class of an object, shows the topological properties of objects, their relationships, etc.).

General geographic maps are used as sources in compiling any thematic maps. They serve as the basis for applying thematic content.

Main part.

At present, taking into account the widespread use of computer technology and GIS technologies, the formalization of the processes of creating maps is one of the urgent tasks

of cartography. As noted by a number of authors [Berlyant, 2005, Kapralov and others, 2005], the introduction of formal procedures into cartographic work makes it possible to automate the most routine and labor-intensive stages of map creation, which frees up time for experiments and creativity in the field of cartographic modeling and map design.

The principal sequence of the formalized creation of maps in a GIS includes 4 main stages; accordingly, the user, in the course of working with a GIS, will have to make a choice 4 times, due to the nature of the scientific or practical task assigned to him and the features of the theme of the map he creates.

At the first stage, in order to form a full and comprehensive idea of the economic structure of a given region among GIS users, information support should include statistical data, on the basis of which information blocks are offered in the GIS:

- social (includes information about the population, labor and employment, standard of living, education, healthcare, offenses);
- economic (contains information about industrial production, agriculture, transport and communications, trade and services to the population, finance, foreign economic activity);
- natural (data on natural resources and environmental conditions).

At the second stage, the user selects the type of map being created, based on the characteristics of the task that he has to solve. Taking into account the results of the analysis of the most typical queries set by GIS users, the following list of typical tasks is proposed that can be solved by the user and can be formalized: determining the density or distribution of any objects or phenomena in a given territory, determining the specific gravity of any objects or phenomena, displaying the structure any object or phenomenon, displaying the dynamics of any object or phenomenon.

At the third stage, the user needs to select the type of source data localization. GIS provides the following options for spatial data referencing:

- localization of data by administrative centers (for example, natural population growth);
- localization of data by administrative regions (for example, the density of paved roads in the regions of a given region);
- localization of data for the region as a whole (for example, indicators of foreign economic activity of a given region).

GIS should be filled with detailed and up-to-date information about natural, social and economic phenomena and objects that have different spatial localization (for administrative centers, for administrative regions and for the region as a whole). Only the presence in the database of various options for spatial data binding will provide the user with sufficient freedom in choosing the type of localization of the source information. Secondly, the user himself must clearly understand the essence and features of the spatial distribution of mapped objects or phenomena, otherwise he will not be able to correctly determine the territorial coverage and scale of the map being created.

At the fourth stage, the user will have to choose a way to present the map he created. Depending on the requirements of the user himself and on the characteristics of the

technical equipment of the workplace where the GIS is installed, the following options are offered:

- presentation of the final result in the form of a digital or electronic map that can be visualized on a computer monitor, or saved to an offline medium (CD or DVD, flash memory, portable hard drive, etc.);
- printing of the created map on paper. Depending on the size of the created map and the required number of copies, printing can be done on a color printer, on a plotter or using other printing equipment;
- publication of the created map on the Internet. When the user selects this option for presenting results, the created map will be automatically converted into a GIS application. The resulting copy of the map in vector data format will allow you to add new information to it and edit already displayed data.

Creation of a map "from scratch", according to independently selected data, a general geographical basis and a notation system. This method is used mainly in three cases - when it is required to display a completely new, previously not sufficiently studied phenomenon of population geography; when it is necessary to show a greater number of parameters than on the available maps of a similar subject, and the previous cartographic bases turn out to be unsuitable for a proper increase in load; and finally, when the map is created for a new territory (there is a refinement of the detail of the thematic map "country-region-location", its transfer to a new territorial device or generalization, the creation of a small-scale map based on larger ones). This method is most effective when creating simple analytical maps. Particular attention here is riveted to the development of a general geographical basis for the map, which is optimal for further plotting this particular topic. The bases for maps of the population of individual regions are usually obtained by processing topographic and survey topographic maps; for atlases, a series of standard bases are developed to ensure the stylistic unity of the maps included in them. Recently, GIS technologies for transforming projections for certain needs are being intensively introduced into thematic mapping. The creation of a map using several source map materials is inherent mainly in synthetic and complex maps in terms of their analytical components. If the mathematical foundations (projections, scales, layouts) of the source maps differ, an additional problem arises in choosing the best option among them. The legend of the created map in most cases will take up a lot of space due to the information richness, which must be taken into account when developing the layout. For complex maps, statistical data should not contradict each other, be taken from one official source (most often it is Stat.uz) and, if possible, refer to one year. For synthetic maps, the load is developed independently, but this requires an extensive database of maps and tables. The development of the thematic content of population maps is the main stage, which consists in determining the necessary system of signs and applying them to the map using the selected methods of cartographic representation.

Table number 1. Common combinations of methods of cartographic representation on population maps:

Sign combinations Use cases

Punsons +

linear signs Joint display of a discrete network of points with linear structures linking them together

Punsons +

quality background Depicting qualitative differences at the same time throughout the territory and for the most important centers

Punsons +

quantitative background Complement of the relative indicator of the continuous dissemination of information through "nodal points"

Punsons +

cartograms Map display of quantity both by regions and by individual items

Linear signs +

ranges Visualization of the general topology of the phenomenon of non-continuous propagation, breaklines and elements

Quality background +

ranges Linking the geography of a phenomenon depicted by areas with a related qualitative indicator

Cartograms +

cartograms Mapping information on absolute and relative indicators on a single grid of regions

Cartograms +

scatter plots One-time display of initial parameters by area units and in a localized aspect

Automatic creation of more complex, complex maps (including methods of cartograms, cartograms, quantitative background, punches, linear signs) based on databases is carried out by GIS applications ArcGis, MapInfo, Panorama, etc.; this is achieved thanks to the classifiers embedded in the GIS - bases of conventional signs associated with the semantics (set of characteristics) of map objects. In addition, it is possible to visualize the parameters of the distribution of the population in the form of a three-dimensional model, which requires appropriate software.

The final stage of creating a thematic map is the development of a legend, additional information, bringing together and arranging all the elements and final design. The map legend is developed together with the map itself and fully reflects the structure of the load - its general geographical part and each thematic parameter. Diagrams, graphs and other clarifying information compiled from the same statistical sources as the map are also given in the legend field. For map charts, the legend often contains a diagram designed in the same way for the entire displayed territory as a whole. In modern maps created by computer methods, the significance of the legend is reduced, as a result of which, as a rule, it is rather compact and does not contain a general geographical element, reflecting the schematic nature of the map itself. The necessary color, line, font design is selected and edited already on the finished electronic map; for these purposes, vector graphics editors

like CorelDraw, Adobe Illustrator or FreeHand are most convenient, providing a wide range of design options.

Conclusion.

By the beginning of the XXI century. The geography of the population of Uzbekistan, as well as geographical science in general, is at a fairly high qualitative and quantitative level of development due to a significant heritage in the form of a knowledge base that has accumulated over the past century and a half, during most of the time periods of which the development of this science in the state occupied leading positions in the world . Population mapping, as an integral part of geography, kept pace with the latter. At the same time, a new type, electronic maps, is characterized by a significant variety of data visualization methods, which became possible due to the introduction of GIS technologies in map production.

REFERENCES:

1. Берлянт А.М. Картография: учебник – 2-е издание, исправленное и дополненное. – М.: КДУ, 2010. – 328 с.
2. Берлянт А.М., Геоинформационное картографирование. Учебник. – М.: Астрей, 1997.
3. Дронов В.П., Барина И.И., Ром В.Я., Лобжанидзе А.А.; под ред. В.П. Дронова. География России: Природа. Население. Хозяйство. 8 кл.: учеб. для 8 кл. общеобразовательных учреждений / 10-е изд., стереотип. – М. : Дрофа, 2009.
4. Кушнырь О.В. Разработка методики картографирования ареалов концентрации населения (диссертация). – М.: МИИГАиК, 2015. – 117 с.
5. Прохорова Е.А. Социально-экономические карты: Учебное пособие. – М.: КДУ, 2010. – 424 с.
6. Сафаров Э.Ю ва бошқалар. Картография ва геовизуализация. Дарслик. Тошкент, «Молия иктисод», 2015.
7. Сафаров Э.Ю. Географик ахборот тизимлари. – Тошкент, Университет, 2010.
8. www.esri.com
9. www.gis-lab.info
10. www.geospatialworld.net